

ASPECTS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT UNIVERSITY

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Abstrakt: In this article we will try to consider some methodological principles and features of teaching a foreign language in a technical university, based on the criteria for the development of professional competence.

The emergence of the concept of competency-based approach - the "competence-based approach" in European higher education entailed a reassessment of the teaching methodology, including teaching a foreign language. The main goals and objectives of the new methodological approach in education were determined by the Commission "Pan-European Format of Foreign Language Proficiency: Training, Teaching, Level Assessment"

Key Words: pedagogical level, methodological level, Projects Method, Case Study Technology, Technology "Debate.

The beginning of the 21st century is characterized by the creation of a global information structure, the transformation of information into an economic category, the development of various information technologies, including in the field of education.

Media education, as a set of means and methods of teaching youth today is more relevant than ever. Changes in education occurring under the influence of the rapid introduction of information technology in all spheres of life, impose serious requirements on the level of competence of a teacher who needs to master the role of a consultant for a student. Researchers and educators from around the world emphasize the special need for media education.

The complex of educational disciplines "Liberal Arts" refers to "objects and skills that in classical antiquity were considered fundamental to the competence of a free person who takes an active part in social and creative life, what in ancient Greece included participation in political, social, philosophical discussions, defense in court, participation in construction, military service. " Grammar, rhetoric, geometry, arithmetic, logic, astronomy formed the basis of Liberal Arts. In the modern world, in the era of globalization of the economy and communications, development of cooperation in all areas of social, political and cultural life, there can be no doubt that English - the language of international

communication, the Internet, science and technology - is an integral part of multidisciplinary education.

Materials and Methods: One of the principles of the competency-based approach in teaching a foreign language at a technical university is "the formulation of learning objectives based on the end result, that is, the acquisition of knowledge, skills, attitudes, values and / or competencies for students to learn and then put into practice after completing an academic period. "

In this regard, in our opinion, the process of teaching a foreign language in a non-philological university, including engineering specialties, should be structured in accordance with and in accordance with relevant educational programs. In the framework of the bachelor's degree in engineering specialties, teaching a foreign language lasts 3 years. The technology "competence-based approach" involves the planning of educational material, focusing on three stages of training depending on the tasks: general training, the basics of phonetics, grammar, speaking practice; specialized training - skills in selecting, scanning, reading texts in a specialty, annotating, preparing messages in a specialty; socio-professional training - an advanced level of language proficiency, which includes the ability to listen and understand lectures in a foreign language, participate in seminars and discussions on professional topics, conduct presentations in the specialty.

At the first stage of linguistic training, the main task is to develop general communication skills - i.e. general competence (speaking skills and reading comprehension).

Conclusion: In addition, communication includes the ability to receive information via the Internet, as well as to provide information for others to use, so students on the Internet can be both consumers and producers of information at the same time.

Among the advantages of learning with the help of new media, among other things, one can note the possibility of self-determination of the educational process, freeing it from temporal and spatial boundaries, optimizing visibility using multimedia, as well as modeling. With the inclusion of new media in pedagogical institutions, a revision of the basic educational and psychological provisions is simultaneously taking place.

Of course, illustrations, pictures, graphics positively affect the storage of textual information. And yet, it should be borne in mind that the simple addition of various sensory perceptions (visual, auditory, tactile) does not automatically lead to an improvement in learning processes. A more important condition for

understanding the use of multimedia in the learning process is the ability to decode character and code systems.

Just as hermeneutical competence is necessary to understand written texts, deciphering hypermedia learning systems requires the ability to understand graphics, animations, and pictures. Quite often, it can be observed that the economical, but targeted use of various medial forms of presentation has greater consequences than the colorful pile of various media presentations of educational material.

In addition, there is a close relationship between thematic interest and knowledge acquisition. A well-organized educational work using the media can be unsuccessful if students show little interest in the proposed topics. The use of media most often brings with it some novelty effect, which can lead to a motivated and interesting presentation (consideration) of the material, but this interest decreases again after a certain time.

The differences between inexperienced users and so-called experts are also important. As modern children and adolescents grow up in a world of strong media influence, the forms of mastering new media technologies should look different than in the case of adults.

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